

THE IMPORTANCE OF REFLECTIVE ACTIVITY IN DEVELOPING LITERACY IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article highlights the role and importance of reflective activity in the process of developing the literacy of preschool children. Through reflective activity, children are justified in analyzing their own thoughts, understanding and correcting their mistakes, forming independent thinking and speech development skills. Also, the effectiveness of the reflective approach in developing children's reading, writing and comprehension skills, and poems about letters for use in classes are shown.

Keywords: preschool education, preparation for school education, literacy, reflective activity, metacognitive, speech development, oral speech, independent thinking, self-assessment, didactic tools, pedagogical approach, game technology, fine motor skills of the fingers.

ВАЖНОСТЬ РЕФЛЕКСИВНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В РАЗВИТИИ ГРАМОТНОСТИ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация: В данной статье освещается роль и важность рефлексивной деятельности в процессе развития грамотности у детей дошкольного возраста. Благодаря рефлексивной деятельности дети получают возможность анализировать собственные мысли, понимать и исправлять свои ошибки, формировать навыки самостоятельного мышления и развития речи. Также показана эффективность рефлексивного подхода в развитии у детей навыков чтения, письма и понимания прочитанного, а также стихотворений о буквах для использования на уроках.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное образование, подготовка к школьному образованию, грамотность, рефлексивная деятельность, метакогнитивный, развитие речи, устная речь, самостоятельное мышление, самооценка, дидактические инструменты, педагогический подход, игровые технологии, мелкая моторика пальцев.

INTRODUCTION

The preschool education sector is the primary link in the continuous education system, and it is of great importance in raising a well-rounded, healthy child and preparing them for school.

Our esteemed President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev pays great attention to the preschool education system and reviewed a number of measures regarding the introduction of modern management mechanisms in preschool education, improvement of the upbringing and educational process, staffing preschool educational organizations with highly qualified specialists, and revising state requirements for organizing quality preschool education taking into account advanced foreign experience in the harmonious development of preschool-age children.

The developments in the scientific field are being widely supported by the state. In particular, the work of raising the younger generation from an early age to be healthy and comprehensively mature, introducing effective forms and methods of education and upbringing into the educational process, and thereby developing children is of great importance.

The adopted regulatory documents create the opportunity to create conditions for the comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of children in preschool educational organizations taking into account advanced foreign experience; to improve the quality of preschool education, to fundamentally improve the quality preparation of children for school in preschool educational organizations, and to introduce modern educational programs and technologies widely used in world practice into the educational process.

One of the current pressing problems is preparing preschool-age children for modern school education, which is being carried out in connection with the modernization of this stage of education. The knowledge that a child must know depends on the successful conduct of activities in preschool educational organizations. Therefore, the leading goal is to develop high qualities in the educator. The educator must teach the child to imagine, to visualize, to work according to a model, to observe various rules and social norms, including rules of conduct, to be able to listen to adults and follow their instructions, to respect the opinions, interests and feelings of others. Practice shows that it is not possible to fully solve this problem with the help of traditional forms of work. For this, the use of modern educational technologies yields great results. Today, a number of teaching technologies, educational and gaming, and health-preserving technologies are being applied in practice.

The attention given to education by the state and the progress in this field is being recognized by parents, strengthening their sense of responsibility regarding their children's education and upbringing. Our parents express their wishes that their children learn to read and write independently as quickly as possible at this age. It should be emphasized here that preparing preschool-age children for school education is a pressing matter.

The preschool education system is an important stage in children's intellectual, speech and social development. In particular, the process of forming literacy creates the foundation for successful reading and writing skills at subsequent stages of education.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

In recent years, early childhood education research has increasingly emphasized the role of reflective activity as the primary mechanism for developing literacy skills in preschool-age children. Reflective activity is generally understood as a form of metacognitive engagement, where children think about their own learning processes, language use and comprehension.

Contemporary research builds on previous theoretical knowledge by combining new perspectives from neuroscience and educational psychology. Recent empirical studies show that dialogic reading and child-directed thinking significantly improve vocabulary acquisition and narrative skills in preschool-age children.

Reflective activity holds special importance in modern pedagogical approaches. The reflection process serves a person's awareness, analysis and evaluation of their own activities. Additionally, Jean Piaget substantiated that cognitive processes in children develop stage by

stage. He stated that the child's intellectual development is formed through analyzing their own experience, reflection activates thinking and prepares for literacy.

American educational scholar John Dewey is considered one of the founders of the theory of reflective thinking. In his work "How We Think," he emphasized that in the educational process, it is important not merely for the child to acquire knowledge, but to reflect on their own experience. In his view, reflection in the educational process helps the child to understand, think about and draw conclusions from their experience; the child achieves independent learning by analyzing their own activity; after each activity the child must think about questions such as "What did I do?", "Why did this happen?", "How can it be improved?"; reflection develops thinking, and the child's independent thinking is the foundation of literacy development. It is precisely through this process that the child's speech develops, logical thinking is formed, and readiness for reading and writing is strengthened.

Lev Vygotsky emphasized the importance of the social environment and inner speech in the educational process, showing that reflective thinking is one of the main factors of development. Lev Vygotsky particularly emphasized the role of social environment and communication in children's development. He considered reflective activity to be closely connected with the child's speech and thinking. According to him, the child begins to understand their own thoughts through communication with adults, develops inner speech, and inner speech is the main factor of literacy. In his work "Mind in Society," Lev Vygotsky emphasized the development of reflective activities in preschool-age children such as discussing fairy tales, question-and-answer, role-playing games, and retelling events.

Maria Montessori was an advocate of giving children free activity. She said that the child's independent work is the most important factor in reflective development. Through this, the child's speech develops, their understanding of letters and sounds becomes easier, and literacy is formed. In the book "The Discovery of the Child," Montessori connected sensory organs and practical activity with reflection in teaching literacy, and stated that giving the child independent activity, understanding and evaluating their own mistakes is the foundation of reflective development, which rapidly develops literacy skills.

Uzbek pedagogical scholars have also put forward important scientific views on the issue of reflective activity in developing literacy of preschool-age children. They have mainly focused on issues of the child's independent thinking, speech development, self-assessment of their activity, and forming literacy through play and communication.

Professor F.R. Qodirova, one of the Uzbek educational scholars, researched the issue of developing cognitive activity in preschool-age children. In the book "Theory of Preschool Education," she emphasizes that the child's active thinking, ability to recognize their own mistakes, and independent organization of speech activity are important in literacy development. According to the scholar, reflection helps the child develop independent thinking, creativity, and communication culture.

N.M. Kayumova, in the textbook "Preschool Pedagogy," gave great importance to communicative activity and speech development in the preschool educational process. According to her views, reflective activity serves the conscious development of the child's speech, and the child acquires literacy skills by analyzing their own thoughts. Kayumova

particularly substantiated the development of reflection through dialogic speech, conversation, and role-playing games.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Reflective activity serves the child's analysis of their own thinking; development of speech and thinking; independent thinking; and formation of literacy skills.

In recent research, reflective activity is considered an effective tool for developing speech and literacy skills in preschool-age children. The research is conducted in preschool educational organizations, using pedagogical observation, experimental and diagnostic methods. During the research process, children's literacy level (letter recognition, sound isolation, reading elements) is assessed.

In the experimental group, reflective activity is organized in the following forms:

- Self-analysis through the question "What did I learn today?"
- Self-assessment of one's work (through visual symbols)
- Group discussion and exchange of opinions

These methods are based on the experiential learning theory developed by John Dewey and David Kolb.

The significance of reflective activity in developing literacy in preschool-age children is that it helps children express their thoughts, correctly pronounce sounds and words, and actively participate in educational and upbringing processes. Instead of simply memorizing letters or words, children begin to understand how and why they read, write, speak and listen.

Reflective activity includes children thinking about what they have heard, said or done — such as discussing a story, explaining their drawings, or recalling events. These experiences reinforce early literacy in several key ways:

- **First, reflection strengthens language development.** When children talk about their experiences or stories, they expand their vocabulary, improve sentence structure and learn to express ideas clearly.

- **Second, it supports comprehension abilities.** Reflecting on stories — asking questions like "What happened?" or "Why did the character act that way?" — helps children understand meaning, sequence, and cause-and-effect relationships that are essential for reading.

- **Third, reflective activity encourages critical thinking.** Even at a young age, children begin to make connections, predict outcomes and form ideas. These skills are foundational for reading comprehension and writing ability later on.

- **Fourth, it increases self-awareness and confidence.** When children reflect on their own learning (for example, realizing that they can identify letters or retell a story), they develop a sense of accomplishment and motivation to learn more.

Finally, reflective practices develop interactive learning. Conversations children have with peers — such as group discussions, storytelling or role-playing games — create a rich language environment where children learn from one another.

In preschool educational organizations, reflective activity can be encouraged through storytelling, guided discussions, drawing and explaining, pretend play, and simple question-and-answer methods. These approaches make literacy development more meaningful and engaging.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Reflective activity is very important because it transforms literacy from passive absorption into an active, thoughtful process and creates a strong foundation for future academic success. During the period up to age 7, oral speech occupies the primary place for a child. Speech is a collection of colorful expressive sounds. It creates the foundation for the child's successful learning at school in the future. "Vocabulary," Q.Shodiyeva emphasized, "gives the child the opportunity to quickly and thoroughly master the knowledge given in all lessons and to express this knowledge and concepts through speech." The development of a child's speech is directly dependent on their vocabulary. It should certainly be noted that the richness of a child's vocabulary is expressed through the child's understanding of the world. The child receives information through observing the environment, through parents, adults, educators, peers, books, films, lessons and games. In all of these, information is given to the child through oral speech. As a result of this, the child's vocabulary must grow, and they must correctly use words, their meanings, grammatically correct sentences, and correct sound pronunciation. This presents certain difficulties for the child. This process requires mental activity from the child. In this regard, systematic educational and upbringing work on developing the child's speech and achieving their literacy must be carried out by educators. These processes are reinforced in preschool educational organizations and mandatory preparatory groups based on the "Ilk qadam" (First Step) state curriculum through speech development lessons, development centers, walks, and excursions. The formation of reading and writing skills in children by educators is carried out through special methodologies appropriate for preschool age.

Preparing preschool-age children for school education and developing literacy within it is subject to the following requirements:

- Creating a comfortable, friendly, safe environment aimed at developing the child;
- Valuing friendly relationships in the children's community;
- Providing education and upbringing based on a child-centered educational approach, organizing educational processes consisting not of lengthy lessons but of games that arouse the child's interest and astonishment;
- Using play as the main educational activity, widely applying didactic tools;
- Taking into account the age characteristics of children, considering their memory, attention, speech and thinking;

- Awakening the child's desire, wish and interest in reading;
- The educational and upbringing processes conducted must be sequential, progressing from simple to complex;
- Systematically developing correct pronunciation of words in the child from an early age, with the educator being demanding of their own speech;
- Building confidence in children to use correct pronunciation, appropriate grammatical forms, diverse sentence constructions and initial writing skills and tools in their speech.

A child wants to write their own name. This process can be organized when the parent brings their child to the preschool educational organization. Parents can write words together with their child using the letters learned, on envelopes attached to their child's clothing locker door, and can also practice writing the child's first name and then last name. One letter must be placed in the envelopes each day. The child must know what kind of letter is placed (its name, whether vowel or consonant). This process can be incorporated into individual work sessions with the child.

Parents also participate in physical education classes at preschool educational organizations. This is a technology aimed primarily at children's physical and mental health. To maintain each child's physical and mental health, the educator, psychologist and the child's parents must work together both in the group and individually in the preschool educational organization. Educators must notice negative behaviors in the child, inform the parents, and begin active work to preserve their mental health. One of the leading activities for preschool-age children is play activity, therefore it is psychologically justified to use various types of children's activities, as well as educational activities conducted through play, in preparing children for school.

Applying pressure to the child by adults, expressing dissatisfaction with the results the child has achieved, is prohibited. The educator must be demanding of their own speech, and the educational and upbringing processes conducted must be sequential, progressing from simple to complex.

Diverse developmental groups can be organized in preschool educational organizations. These are preschool educational groups organized taking into account the wishes of parents. The organization of such groups allows for fuller use of the cultural opportunities of society in raising preschool-age children. Such groups are based on children's talents in various directions (visual arts, creativity, literature and arts, foreign languages, physical education, music, school first-grade preparatory groups, etc.). The purpose of this is the comprehensive development of preschool-age children and the full implementation of the preschool education curriculum. The developmental environment of educational content must correspond to the age and psychological characteristics of children, and it is also important that educational and upbringing processes are conducted on the basis of family and parent communities. In preparing children for school education, it is required to devise forms of interaction with families and parents together with specialists in this field, and to specially develop a system of mutual cooperation.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that through organizing children's activities in the pedagogical process, the educator-teacher develops initiative and independence in each child, the desire to find a reasonable and worthy path in various life situations, interest in and adaptation to studying at school. At the current stage of development of our society, innovative processes primarily affect the preschool education system, as this is the initial stage of revealing the child's potential abilities. The development of the preschool education system and the transition to a new quality level cannot be achieved without developing innovative technologies. Innovation is a pedagogical practice aimed at the child's personality and developing their abilities. In the current changing environment, a preschool education teacher must have the ability to use a wide range of various integrative approaches to child development and modern technologies to prepare and adapt children for school education. Reflective activity is of great importance in developing literacy in preschool-age children. It has a positive effect on children's self-awareness, independent thinking and speech development. Based on modern research, it is appropriate to widely introduce reflective methods into the preschool education system.

In general conclusion, we can say that preparing children for school education at ages 6–7 creates the opportunity for them to master school curricula well in the future, as well as to manifest their aspirations and abilities. In preparing children for school, preschool childhood plays a special role in the process of forming human thinking and the human personality in general, and serves to raise the conscious generation of our society.

The results obtained show that reflective activity is an important pedagogical tool in preschool education. Reflection allows children to consciously acquire knowledge and evaluate their own activities.

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